

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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DIRECTIONS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: Digital tourism development in Uzbekistan is a key foundation for rapid economic growth. This article examines the potential of digital systems and platforms in the tourism sector to improve service quality, stimulate domestic and inbound tourism, promote national tourism products internationally, effectively manage tourist flows, and modernize tourism infrastructure.

Keywords: digital technologies, tour operator, travel agent, service quality, domestic tourism, inbound tourism, digital transformation, innovative services, tourism infrastructure, digital marketing, smart tourism, strategic management.

Аннотация: Направления развития туризма в Узбекистане на основе цифровых технологий являются важной основой для стремительного развития экономики. Данная статья рассматривает возможности использования цифровых систем и платформ в туристическом секторе для повышения качества услуг, стимулирования внутреннего и въездного туризма, продвижения национальных туристических продуктов на международном рынке, эффективного управления потоками туристов и модернизации туристической инфраструктуры.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, туроператор, турагент, качество услуг, внутренний туризм, въездной туризм, цифровая трансформация, инновационные услуги, туристическая инфраструктура, цифровой маркетинг, интеллектуальный туризм, стратегическое управление.

Annotatsiya: O'zbekistonda turizmni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari iqtisodiyotni jadal taraqqiyotining muhim asoslari hisoblanadi. Ushubu maqolada turizm sohasida raqamli tizimlar va platformalarning xizmatlar sifatini oshirish, ichki va kiruvchi turizmni rag'batlantirish, hamda xalqaro bozorda milliy turizm mahsulotlarini targ'ib qilish yo'llari, sayyohlar oqimini samarali boshqarish va turizm infratuzilmasini modernizatsiya qilishda raqamli texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, turoperator, turagent, xizmatlar sifati, ichki turizm, kiruvchi turizm, raqamli transformatsiya, innovatsion xizmatlar, turizm infratuzilmasi, raqamli marketing, smart turizm, strategik boshqaruv.

INTRODUCTION

The development of Uzbekistan's tourism sector based on digital technologies is a priority of state policy. Therefore, comprehensive measures are being implemented at the state level to bring the tourism infrastructure into line with modern requirements through digital transformation. This creates opportunities for Uzbekistan's long-term integration into the global tourism market through the use of digital solutions in the development of tourism services and the creation of marketing and information platforms. The development of digital tourism requires the development of the national economy, which is directly linked to the strategy for transition to a digital economy. Therefore, within the framework of the "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" strategy, information and communication technologies are being introduced into all sectors, including tourism, which will expand the reach of digital services and ensure economic efficiency.

At the same time, as a new direction in the digitalization of tourism, special priority is given to the development of eco-tourism. In particular, Decree No. 217[1] of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to create a management system capable of promptly responding to the needs of the population in the field of ecology and tourism," adopted on November 18, 2025, creates a new legal and economic framework in this area. This article aims to examine the development trends of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan based on digital technologies, their impact on service efficiency, and their contribution to the national economy.

A REVIEW OF THE RELEVANT LITERATURE

The topic of tourism development using digital technologies has been actively studied by local scholars in Uzbekistan in recent years. Published research articles on this topic focus on three main areas: the implementation of digital systems, improving service quality, and the digitalization of regional tourism.

According to Academician N. Tukhliyev of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2], this focus places particular emphasis on defining tourism as a “dynamically developing area of the creative economy based on creativity and new ideas,” which will open up new opportunities for tourism and become an important foundation for its digitalization.

A number of other researchers have conducted research in this area and prioritized the following areas. K. Kuchkarov’s article, “Possibilities of Implementing Digital Tourism Management Systems,” emphasizes the importance of creating electronic booking systems, mobile applications, and databases in tourism organizations [3]. The author notes that the introduction of information and communication technologies allows for the acquisition of real-time information about cultural heritage sites, hotels, and tourist routes; on the other hand, he substantiates this with evidence that these systems significantly improve the quality of tourist service.

Also, in the article “Development of Intelligent Tourism in Uzbekistan,” U. Narzullaeva and N. Abzalova present a statistical analysis of the effectiveness of digital services in the tourism sector. The author demonstrates an increasing trend in meeting customer needs through an electronic booking system and conducts a comparative analysis of digital indicators of the economic efficiency of digital services [4].

In the article “Status and Directions for the Implementation of Intelligent Technologies in the Tourism Sector of Uzbekistan,” Sh. Kutfiddinov analyzes the impact of online platforms, social media, and electronic advertising on the image of regional tourism. The author confirms with experimental data that digital marketing is an effective tool for presenting tourism resources to a foreign audience [5].

These research articles provide in-depth coverage of the theoretical foundations of digital tourism development in Uzbekistan and demonstrate in practice that the introduction of digital services has improved service quality and economic indicators. Their overall conclusion is that digital technologies play an important role in improving the level of services in the tourism sector, automating information exchange and effectively promoting national tourism potential.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article examines the development of tourism in Uzbekistan using digital technologies, based on documentary analysis and empirical methods. Data was collected from official statistics and reports from tourism organizations. Quantitative analysis was conducted on the electronic booking system and tourist flow. Qualitative data was used to assess the effectiveness of digital services. Econometric analysis and regression methods helped determine the impact of digital systems on tourism services. Thus, the methodology allowed us to evaluate the effectiveness of digital transformation in the tourism sector.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The development of the tourism sector in our country based on digital technologies requires an in-depth study of the sector’s development. In particular, in this regard, as noted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev in his Address to the Oliy Majlis and the People of Uzbekistan on December 26, 2025 [6], he set a priority strategic goal for the tourism sector: attracting 20 million foreign tourists by 2030 and increasing the volume of tourism services to \$20 billion. In particular, based on the President’s directive “Increase GDP from \$240 billion by 2030...”[6], the share of tourism services in the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to our calculations, will amount to 8.3 percent by 2030. According to the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tourism sector in our Republic has a systematic development trend in 2020-2025 (Table 1).

Table 1.
Tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan: Tourist activity in 2021-2025[7]

Year	Inbound Tourism (thousands)	Outbound tourism (thousands)	Domestic tourism (thousands)
2020	2475	4472	3880
2021	4999	5163	5346

2022	4595	5590	6748
2023	5860	4698	4999
2024	8 000	5 300	8 500
2025	11 700	6 000	10 000

This statistical table shows that inbound tourism figures demonstrated significant growth in 2021, with the number of tourists increasing. Domestic tourism activity also continued to grow through 2022, reaching a higher level in 2023. This growth trend indicates expanding demand for tourism services and the opportunities for service delivery through the introduction of digital technologies.

The data in the following chart can be used to analyze tourism statistics (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Number of Tour Operators, Travel Agents, and Other Organizations Providing Services in the Tourism Sector of Uzbekistan (as of February 1, 2026)[8]

The digitalization of tourism in Uzbekistan is directly linked to the growing number of organizations providing tourism services. According to the National Statistical Committee, the number of tour operators, travel agents, and other organizations providing tourism services in Uzbekistan was 1,841 in 2022. This figure reached 2,374 in 2023, 2,539 in 2024, and 2,592 in 2025. As of February 1, 2026, this number had increased to 3,143, indicating rapid growth in the industry.

This growth trend demonstrates the effectiveness of digitalization. Electronic booking systems, online platforms, and digital marketing tools facilitate the expansion of tour operators' activities. This improves service quality, effectively manages tourist flows, and modernizes tourism infrastructure. Thus, the increase in the number of tour operators and the integration of digital solutions contribute to the strengthening of digital tourism development in Uzbekistan.[9] Collecting and processing tourism statistics using digital systems is important for monitoring and forecasting tourism services. Automated data collection is carried out through digital platforms—online booking platforms, interactive statistical portals, and mobile applications—which facilitates the development of tourism using digital technologies. Overall, statistical analysis shows that the introduction of digital technologies enhances the provision of services in the tourism sector, improves forecasting of tourist flows, and enhances tourism's contribution to the national economy [10].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

An analysis of current digital tourism development processes in Uzbekistan yielded several important conclusions. In our opinion, these are the following:

First, digital transformation allows for a significant improvement in the quality of services in the tourism sector. Establishing interactive communication between tourists and tourism organizations through electronic

booking systems, online platforms, and mobile applications will increase the efficiency of service delivery and improve customer service. All of this, based on the objectives set out in the Address, will create the opportunity, according to our calculations, to increase the share of tourism services in the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan to 8.3% by 2030.

Secondly, the effective use of new digital technologies, including the widespread use of artificial intelligence, will create opportunities for analyzing and forecasting the development of the tourism sector based on data collected through digital technologies.

Thirdly, through the widespread introduction of digital technologies, we will develop opportunities for introducing Uzbekistan's national tourism products to the international market, thereby enhancing the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the global tourism market and creating conditions for improving the Republic's image in this area and strengthening its competitiveness. Based on the conducted research, we can offer the following recommendations:

- widespread implementation of digital platforms and electronic systems in the tourism sector, their full integration into the activities of tourism organizations.
- ensuring interactivity and user-friendliness of digital services for tour operators and travel agencies, as well as developing mechanisms for assessing and monitoring service quality.
- extensive use of digital marketing and online advertising tools to present Uzbekistan's tourism products to an international audience and strengthen the brand's image.
- implementation of innovative digital solutions to stimulate domestic tourism and develop new tourist destinations.
- developing a strategy for effective tourism management using digital technologies by strengthening public-private partnerships (ppps), etc.

Overall, the development of tourism, considered the driving force of our country's economy, through digital technologies creates new creative opportunities for the sector's development.

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